

METHODS OF FORMATION OF SPEECH SKILLS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

It requires the formation of a form of literary and artistic speech through practical, regular and consistent teaching of the mother tongue based on examples and special exercises. The main task of elementary school mother tongue classes is to prepare students for educational activities, to form a person who can communicate with others, who can convey his thoughts to others in an understandable way.

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained state independence, the fundamental improvement of the structure and content of education of secondary educational institutions, in particular, primary education students, is becoming a priority. For this purpose, the National Personnel Training Program was approved in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education, and it is "science based on national and universal moral values, work skills, creative thinking, conscious attitude to the world and choosing a profession. aimed at ensuring the acquisition of systematic knowledge on the basics, strengthening the need to acquire knowledge, basic educational, scientific and general cultural knowledge, and the formation of spiritual and moral qualities. In particular, the formation of speech culture in primary classes is an urgent issue today. Working on the correctness of speech Improving the speech culture of elementary school students is considered one of the main areas of the teacher's educational and methodological activity. The issue of the formation of speech culture occupied a central place in the works of Eastern thinkers of the distant past. Farobiy says the following about speaking correctly, making logical conclusions, and being a meaningful and beautiful speaker, how to teach and receive, how to express, explain, how to ask and when we come to answer, I affirm that:

➤ The first of the sciences about this is the science of language, which gives names to bodies, that is, substance (independent, self-existent) and accidentia (accidental manifestation).

- The second science is grammar: it teaches how to arrange the names given to bodies, and how to compose words of wisdom and speech expressing the arrangement of substance and accident, and the result.
- The third science is logic: it teaches us how to arrange propositions according to logical figures in order to produce certain conclusions, by means of which we can know what we do not know and judge what is true and what is false. Speech the term is derived from the Arabic word, speaking, speech; means the ability to speak. Use of language in the processes of expression and exchange of ideas; the process of the speaker's use of language tools and the product of this process.

It is known that many people have been interested in the place and role of speech and thinking in human life since ancient times. Today, in our country, which is accelerating on the path of innovative development, education of a mature generation, education of enlightened and highly moral citizens is one of the priority directions of our state's policy. Also, we should pay great attention to the future of young people. The most important thing is that in elementary schools, first of all, the development of children's speech culture and elimination of them, and moreover, speech is one of the important main tasks for their fluency. Speech is the process of using a unique weapon called language, which performs very important tasks, and the manifestation of the possibilities of language units in relation to phenomena such as existence, thinking, consciousness and situation. Speech is a language in motion, it appears in the process of movement of speech organs and consists of words and sentences. The concept of speech culture, the desire to speak culturally, is a long-standing phenomenon in all national languages. This concept is related to certain linguistic norms, ethical and aesthetic requirements.

Speech means the process of speaking and its result. In fact, speech is one of the highest, complex, spiritual tasks of a human being. It is a unique function of a person, which was created as a means of exchange of ideas between people in the process of social work. A person perceives objects and events in the external world with the help of sensory organs and speech. Study the practical importance of melodiousness, i.e. reading with recitation, in standardizing students' oral and written speech, ensuring their proportionality, defining the nature and distinctive features of the national language, and reflecting the laws of expression and pronunciation. it is necessary to observe the standards and criteria of the literary language, to search for ways to improve reading and study methods, and to put the most convenient ones into practice. To study the real personal characteristics of the individual style of education of speech development in elementary school students and to develop the fluency of students' speech.

The development of speech in elementary school students is carried out on the basis of independent analysis, comprehensive mutual descriptions, teacher's observations. The leading place of all the activities conducted in the primary class, mother tongue classes is the development of speech, which includes the tasks of teaching literacy, forming beautiful writing skills, and expanding the scope of thinking. In these lessons, it is necessary to aim for more practical goals, to form the skills of using language resources in speech, to think creatively, and to educate students' language sensitivity. Regular development of their oral speech will provide practical help in creating a coherent speech and text. One of the main tasks of primary school teachers is to pay attention to the speech of primary school students and the speech culture while they are speaking. Teachers should consider different ways to improve the speaking

culture of students, the reason is that they have the cultural ability to speak when they participate in classes and various events, and to attract the audience, as well as to be able to immediately imitate their speech. etc. are important.

Therefore, we must eliminate the shortcomings in the speech of students from the time they go to school. Texts from primary school textbooks and interesting fairy tales play an important role in overcoming these speech defects. Below, we will give an opinion on several different ways of improving speech culture:

For example: the methods mentioned above are very useful in improving speech culture. For example, teaching them to read while introducing the language to speech first. Teaching to read means reading and teaching them in a meaningful way before making them ready for speaking. When we say beautiful writing, it is understood to copy our speech on white paper in accordance with the rules of etiquette, following the etiquette of speech culture. There is an aphorism from our ancestors that says "beautiful writing is also an art". Literacy is considered the most important part of these examples. If we don't know how to read such words, we can neither read nor write, therefore, literate reading forces us to speak fluently and beautifully. Based on the linguistic concepts included in the elementary school mother tongue program, exercises can be divided into phonetic, lexical, word formation, morphemic (word structure), graphic, orthographic, orthoepic, grammatical exercises.

The analysis carried out on the basis of these exercises is comprehensive in terms of helping students to master theoretical concepts, enriching their vocabulary, and developing their connected speech.

It should be noted that the primary class does not have the opportunity to analyze the language of the exercise texts in the mother tongue textbooks, the questions developed on them, and to gradually develop the students' speech. Although all exercise texts in native language textbooks help to strengthen and expand theoretical knowledge, they cannot be the basis for students' vocabulary enrichment, speech development, and practical acquisition of the language.

The fact that the exercises have not achieved perfection as a system, they are composed of thematic sentences intended to provide theoretical information, undoubtedly, the exercises have little positive effect on the acquisition of connected speech. A poor text in the form of ordinary conversational speech cannot be a source for enriching the student's speech. Pupils' acquisition of the Uzbek literary language depends on the artistry of the exercise texts, the richness of language components.

Conducting lessons by means of didactic games also helps children to engage in mental activity faster and to develop adaptation. Didactic games can be used at the beginning of a new lesson or during the reinforcement of a previous lesson to increase students' interest in the lesson.

Here are some examples of games that can be used in elementary school mother tongue lessons: Chain game. The teacher says a word that rhymes in the language, the students find a word that has a meaning in the order of the table and say it. When there is no meaning left, the next student himself helps to continue the game by saying a word that has a meaning in the language. A number of desk pupils can form groups of words with several meanings. The game continues in sequence. For example, if there are 10 pupils sitting in a row, they can form groups of three or four rhyming words.

Thus, as for the last speech activity, all the examples given above are expressed in the last method. The more we read, write and pronounce correctly, the last method will come naturally. As long as everyone learns these speech activities, not everyone will be wrong. People who read a lot of books, their worldview, inner world, and the world they live in become true. Nomads say that "look at life with your own eyes", which means that you have learned to think correctly in life.

That is why these speech activities are very important in our life. Such methods play an important and fundamental role in the development of students' speech and in their correct and fluent pronunciation.

In elementary grades, such methods are first explained to the students by the teacher, and later, over the years, it is important for children to be able to read correctly, correctly pronounce, and correctly approach the questions asked. As we mentioned above, the most important things in improving speech culture are the reading books, speaking styles, and beautiful pronunciation, which are important tools in developing speech.

In conclusion, we can say that elementary school students who have just come from pre-school educational institutions may not be able to pronounce words correctly, because of this, they have been mispronouncing words even while teasing their parents. If we teach each letter they pronounce together with the syllables, each student's speech will be correct and the pronunciation will be beautiful.

REFERENCES:

1. Solieva, Z. B., & Javburieva, R. USE OF GAMES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 18.
2. Солиева, З. Б. ПРОБЛЕМА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЧЕСКОЙ ОБРАБОТКИ СЛОВА И СПОСОБЫ ЕЕ РЕШЕНИЯ. *УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА*, 27.
3. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). Анализ человеческой психики в повестях. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
4. Эшматова, Ю. (2022). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ПСИХОЛОГИЗМА В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ. *ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 155-161.
5. Boymaxmatovna, E. Y. (2022). WRITER'S SKILL AND LANDSCAPE IMAGE. *ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 143-146.
6. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). О 'ZGA TILLI GURUHLARDA SHE'RLARNING JANR XUSUSIYATLARINI FARQLASHGA O 'RGATISH. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
7. Eshmatova, Y. (2022). ЎЗБЕК АЁЛИ РУҲИАТИНИНГ ЁРИТИЛИШИДА ЯНГИ ҚИРРАЛАРНИНГ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz)*, 23(23).
8. МАМАТҚУЛОВ, В. (2024). О 'ZBEKISTON JANUBIY VILOYATLARIDA SANOAT KORXONALARINING TASHKIL ETILISHI VA HUDUDLAR SANOATINING IXTISOSLASHUVI JARAYONINING TARIXIY TAHLILI (1930-1950 yy). *News of UzMU journal*, 1(1.2. 1).
9. Sherozovich, M. B. (2024). INDUSTRIAL MEASURES IN UZBEKISTAN 1925-1954 AND THEIR RESULTS (in the case of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions). *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 195-200.
10. Sherozovich, M. B., & Shuhratovna, M. N. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF FOOD INDUSTRIES IN THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND CONSEQUENCES. *World scientific research journal*, 24(1), 188-194.
11. Sherozovich, M. B. (2024). CONFLICT SITUATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING INDUSTRY PERSONNEL IN SURKHANDARYA AND KASHKADARYA REGIONS: HISTORICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS (1925-1950). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 221-225.
12. Sherozovich, M. B., & Shuhratovna, M. N. (2024). THE EMERGENCE OF THE GAS-SULFUR INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT HISTORY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF KASHKADARYA REGION). *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 39(5), 217-220.
13. Rustamkulovna, S. T. (2022). SOCIAL FACTORS OF ETHNOCULTURAL TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(4), 622-626.
14. Сафарова, Т. Р. (2022). ЗАМОНАВИЙ ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ФАЛСАФАНИ ЎҚИТИШНИНГ ВАЗИФАЛАРИ ВА МУАММОЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(9), 657-664.
15. Сафарова, Т. Р. (2021). ВЛИЯНИЕ ПАНДЕМИИ COVID-19 НА СОСТОЯНИЕ ЭТНОКУЛЬТУРНОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In *Новые вызовы новой науки: опыт теоретического и эмпирического анализа* (pp. 176-183).
16. Kholdarova, F. (2017). SOME ASPECTS OF NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN POLITICAL NEGOTIATIONS. In *Перспективы развития научных исследований в 21 веке* (pp. 149-150).

17. Kholdarova, F. (2017). SOME ASPECTS OF NATIONAL PECULIARITIES IN POLITICAL NEGOTIATIONS. In *Перспективы развития научных исследований в 21 веке* (pp. 149-150).
18. Холдарова, Ф. Т. (2018). Стратегия повышения эффективности политических переговоров Узбекистана в регионе Центральной Азии. In *Theory and practice of scientific research* (pp. 268-270).
19. Ugli, I. J. T., Tuxtabayevna, K. F., & Ugli, I. S. T. (2020). Comparison of Similes and Metaphors in Translations (In Act of Beneficent Knowledge). *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(05).
20. Очилова, Г. А., Жумаева, Ш. С., & Курбонова, М. Б. (2019). Политика межнациональных отношений и толерантность в Узбекистане. *Наука, образование и культура*, (9 (43)), 15-18.
21. Жумаева, Ш. С., & Очилова, Г. А. (2019). ТВОРЧЕСКАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ И ЕЁ ГУМАНИСТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ. *Научное знание современности*, (2), 5-10.
22. Навои, А. (2016). Проблема этических норм развития науки в трудах мыслителей средневековой Средней Азии. *Молодой учёный*, 6, 670.
23. Жумаева, Ш. С. (2023). АХБОРОТ ХАВФСИЗЛИГИ ВА МАФКУРАВИЙ ҲИМОЯ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5 SPECIAL), 286-290.
24. Suyunovna, J. S. (2023). The Culture of Reading as a Phenomenon of Spiritual Life. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(5), 84-87.
25. Taxirovna, A. S. LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS IN THE TRANSLATION OF STORIES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS, 2023/2/c12.
26. Taxirovna, A. S. (2024). COLLABORATIVE LEARNING: FOCUSING ON TECHNIQUES THAT PROMOTE TEAMWORK AND SHARED KNOWLEDGE AMONG STUDENTS, SO 'NGI ILMIIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI.
27. Taxirovna, A. S. (2023). Lingua-cultural aspects of the translation of English and Uzbek stories, Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany).
28. Mamatkulov, B. (2021). Conflicts of the process of the industrial staff training in the soviet period. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 507-510.
29. Mamatkulov, B. (2021, November). A New Interpretation of Industry in Uzbekistan During Independence. In "ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 158-161).
30. Маматкулов, Б. (2023). О 'ЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГАЗ-ОЛТИНГУГУРТ САНОАТИНИНГ ЮЗАГА КЕЛИШИ ВА УНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШ ТАРИХИ (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA). *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(12/1).
31. Suyunovna, J. S. (2023). Combination of Mythological, Religious and Philosophical Worldviews.
32. Алиева, З. Р. (2020). Роль дистанционного обучения в методике преподавания русского языка как иностранного. *Молодой ученый*, (35), 176-178.
33. Алиева, З. Р. (2024). ТЕОРИЯ РЕЧЕВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИКИ. *SCHOLAR*, 2(5), 121-126.

34. Kakharova, D. S. (2020). CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(2), 337-342.
35. Кахарова, Д. С. БЎЛАЖАК ЎЎҚИТУВЧИНИНГ ИЖОДИЙ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИ ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ CREATIVITY OF THE FUTURE TEACHER Саидова Гулрух Ҳалим қизи.
36. Ахмедов, О. С. (2010). Лексико-семантические проблемы при переводе с английского языка налоговых и таможенных терминов. *Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики*, (1-2), 18-21.
37. Ахмедов, О. С. (2014). Калькирование в налоговой и таможенной терминосистеме узбекского языка. *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (3 (332)), 12-15.

